

Assessment of Causes of Mental Health Challenges among Retirees in Ifelodun Local Government Area of Kwara State, Nigeria

*Aminu, Hammed Popoola Ph.D.¹

Email: hammedpopoola@gmail.com

Tel: +2348137358387

Ehindero, Elizabeth Ronke

Email: ronkeehindero@gmail.com;

Tel: +2347038746113

Aminullahi, Salman Alawaye Ph.D.

Email: aminullahi.sa@unilorin.edu.ng;

Tel: +2348038526722

¹Department of Counsellor Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

Abstract

Mental health problem has gained research interest in the recent years among researchers. Mental health underlies the extent to which individual functions cognitively, emotionally, socially and physically. The retirees had been statistically found to have decreased quality life due to psychological conditions that can be clinically diagnosed and treated. Thus, the study examined "causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State". Descriptive design was adopted for the study and multi-stage sampling method of purposive, stratified and simple random sampling technique. The samples of the study comprise of one hundred and twenty (120) retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State, Nigeria. The researchers used "Causes of Mental Health Challenges Questionnaire (CMHCQ)" to elicit relevant information from the respondents for the study. The instrument was subjected to test re-test reliability statistical method and result from this exercise yielded 0.86 reliability coefficient. Frequency counts and percentages were used for demographic data. The null hypotheses formulated were analysed using t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at .05 level of significance. The findings of the study indicated that the major causes of mental health challenges are; absence of functional intervention programme, brain malfunction/defect/injury and financial unpreparedness. The hypotheses tested revealed no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges as expressed by retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on gender and religion but significant difference was noticed based on year of retirement. Based on the outcomes of the study, some recommendations were made.

Keywords: Causes, Mental-Health, Challenges, Retirees.

Introduction

The lives of the retired civil servant individuals in Nigeria have been characterized by multifarious mental-health challenges in a continuum of tormenting experience with little or no assistance to alleviate their pains. It is on records that many of the retired civil servants in Nigeria have experienced one form of mental-health condition or the other after their retirement, which has hindered the quality of life that they had previously enjoyed while they were in active service. Mental-health has been regarded as a state of an individual emotional, psychological and social well-being. It is a state of balance in someone's psychological, physiological and social life that has resulted in experience of mental wellbeing, quality life and emotional stability over a long span of time in an individual's life. To live happily within and outside oneself, is primarily a function of maintenance of good mental health which could be linked to harmonious relationship between the soul and the body of any living man. Wang (2022) affirmed that since the mid of 20th century, the understanding of people about mental health has gone through a certain transformation process which has diverted their focus from a mere understanding of illness to wellness, which has formed the basic requirement for getting rid of illness from the body, and to the desire of comprehensive positive mental functioning. Galderisi, et al. (2017) stated that the definition of mental health which was proposed by the World

Assessment of Causes of Mental Health ... (Aminu, et. al., 20203) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408112>

Health Organization (WHO) has been centred around a hedonic and eudemonic perspective of human existence, in which a major role is assigned to an individual's well-being and productivity. However, well-being in this term is regarded as a desirable goal for majority of human beings, and its inclusion in the of mental health definition raises some concerns among scholars. According Galderisi, et al. (2017), people's well-being includes emotional, psychological and social well-being, and it evolves around positive feelings (such as, happiness and satisfaction), positive attitudes towards self, personal responsibilities and towards other people around oneself and a positive functioning (such as, social integration, actualization and coherence). Summarily, mental health can be regarded as a state of well-being in which an individual realizes his or her own potentials, has the ability to cope with the normal stressors of life, ability to work productively and fruitfully, and ability to make a contribution to one's own community. Mental health is a comprehensive system that is so related to people's physical health, lifestyle and socioeconomic status, which underpins the overall wellness and functionality of anybody. Unfortunately, the widespread use of the word mental health has been restricted to absence of mental illness in an individual, in a number of societies. This therefore calls for a comprehensive approach to its definition, diagnosis and treatment.

Wang (2022) stressed that mental health as the ability in an individual to handle normal life stresses, realizing his or her potential and the ability to integrate into the community that he or she belongs. However, there is little agreement on this definition according to Galderisi, et al. (2017). Patel, et al. (2013) observed that the lack of consensus on mental wellness is still a major obstacle for integrating mental health initiatives into global health programmes and primary healthcare services across the globe, and recently there are agitations that mental health might not be something that can be achieved generally, rather, it could be assigned to an ability of an individual to adapt and to manage self successfully in the face of life challenges which has shown a trend of changing the definition of mental health from a universal standard to a comprehensive ability that are strongly related to individual differences in term of personal characteristics. Galderisi, et al. (2017) affirmed further that mental health is a dynamic or active state of internal equilibrium that allows anybody to use his or her innate abilities in harmonious relationship with the universal values or standards of his or her society. The above authors also stressed that the maintenance of mental health entails processing of basic cognitive or mental ability and social skills, ability to recognize things accordingly, expression of, and adapt to one's own emotions, as well as empathic understanding of other peoples' feelings, flexibility in behavioural dispositions and ability to cope with adverse life occurrences, function appropriately in certain social conditions, and having harmonious relationship between body and mind. All of the aforementioned attributes represented important components of good mental health which have all contributed, to a varying degree, to the state of internal equilibrium.

The concept of mental health cannot be exclusively arrived at and as such, no universally agreed definition available for the construct, but a real definition of course, must be focused on the ability of an individual to pay attention, remember things and organize information, solve problems, make decisions, and use one's own repertoire of verbal/non-verbal abilities to communicate and interact with other people in the society (Galderisi, et al., 2017). Mental health problem or mental health illness refers to such a condition in the life of an individual which affects his or her cognition, emotion, and behaviour. In the middle of last century according to Wang (2022), mental disorders did not have a broad classification and patients, meanwhile, its definition was only depending on diagnosis alone. However, due to the aggressively increase in the number of patients that were experiencing mental health challenges in every society, existing medical resources seems not enough to cater for their treatments, the new classifications were highly needed to identify patients based on their needs, experiences and peculiarities and give them a corresponding treatment based on identified variables (Haruna & Mayanchi, 2023). Nowadays, the definition of mental illness has indeed moved from a partial one to a more holistic perspective or it has moved away from a simple concept about a disease, to a more comprehensive understanding of health challenges in some individualistic and general perspectives. There are difference causal factors of mental health problems which individual may experience at any given time. Many of which have gained empirical evidences nowadays, although such empirical evidences are scarce in Nigeria. Different theories have been proposed to explain the reason why people have mental health challenges. Among such theories are; "Social Causation Theory (Jon Ivar & Steinar, 2003) and Rational Emotive Behavioural Theory (REBT) of Albert Ellis. The Social Causation Theory believed that individual's social environment accounts for his or her mental health conditions. Another theory that explains the reasons why people develop psychological disorder is "Rational Emotive Behavioural Theory" (REBT) which was propounded by Albert Ellis. The theory is also known as ABC Theory. This theory maintains that the reason why some people develop mental health problems was largely due to the belief formed over time by such an individual on certain event of his or her life and that not the event per se that directly leads to the psychological condition. Ellis referred to event that befell individual as activating agent, which does not directly link to consequence (A-B-C), but directly link to belief formed from the event that occurs in the life of an individual. Across literature, the leading causes of mental health challenges are factors such as; experience of childhood abuse, traumatic experience, experience of social and neglect or isolation and loneliness,

Assessment of Causes of Mental Health ... (Aminu, et. al., 20203) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408112>

discrimination and stigmatization, social disadvantage, poverty and overwhelming debts, bereavements, severe or long-term stress, long-term physical health problem among other causal factors.

Retirement is regarded as the exit of an individual from active service usual at a fixed period of time or age such as 35 years of service or 60-year-old depending which one comes first, one when an individual is no longer capable of rendering effective service due to a particular condition. Retirement in a public or private organization is a legal, authorized and formal ending of work life and it is a shift from active involvement in the world of work to the active world of leisure Temilola (2022). The above author stated that just as retirement makes a period of transition in the lives of people, the nature of retirement is in itself experiencing of a period of transition as well and as a result of lack of applicable and sustainable interventions, many people have experienced a variety of psychosomatic challenges, and some of them show signs of psycho-phobic reactions. According to Temilola (2022) in Nigeria, both the public and private sectors regard retirement as the most intractable or difficult experience, and it has even come to the point that retirement challenges have made post-retirement life so terrible that many Nigerian workers are being feverish and fearful of going for retirement. According to Ugwu and Idemudia (2023), the psychological implication of retirement is under emphasized. The above authors maintained further that a proactive personality negatively predicted retirement anxiety, and that social comparison (opinion) mediated the relationship between proactive personality and retirement anxiety (financial preparedness and social alienation), and that social comparison (opinion and ability) mediated the relationship between proactive personality and retirement anxiety. They stressed further that retirees in Nigeria faced with complex challenges which include; financial unpreparedness, social alienation, and uncertainty. Temilola (2022) affirmed in his study that insufficient financial resources due to lack of retirement planning and absence of income generating activities represented the topmost post-retirement challenges that the older retirees are often faced with. The above author also maintained that reduced in the levels of physical activity combined with old age constituted one of the major causes of health challenges among his study participants. Another major post retirement challenge discovered by Temilola (2022) was the absence of functional government interventions for the retirees. However, it appears as if retirement is a curse that usually associates with a painful and provocative experience only in many Nigerian societies. Daramola, et al. (2019) in another empirical endeavour discovered that there are usually three main challenges confronting this age group. The first of these challenges according to the above authors was poverty, due to loss or reduction of earning power, while the second one was the increasing prevalence of chronic diseases among the retirees and older population in Nigeria, with the accompanying increased healthcare utilization and financial burdens on them. They also observed that elderly people's abuse has been gaining attention as a major social problem among researchers. According to them, tackling this menace requires a multidimensional approach, joint collaborations and involvement of a number of stakeholders, hinging on strong political will and political commitment on the part of government, which is critical for effective implementation of any policy at all. Daramola, et al. (2019) maintained further that it is essential to engage all stakeholders including; governments, institutions, organizations, civil society groups, private sector, community leaders, youth and youth groups, health-care providers, researchers, caregivers, families, older people, and the general public towards capacities building among populace for translating the internationally agreed policy frameworks into practical effects by ensuring that older persons such as retirees in Nigeria, do enjoy income security, gain access to health care and not being subjected to any form of abuse or inhuman treatment.

Ejeh, et al. (2019) reported that emotional health problems are common or prevalent among retirees, but they are often remaining undetected and untreated. According to them, emotional health problems occur to the retirees as a result of challenge that is experienced by them, and complex interaction of social, psychological and biological factors play the major role. Their study unveiled that there were significant relationships between depression and retirees' demographic factors of gender, age and educational level with 5% of the variation experiences of depression among retirees. There were also significant relationships between anxiety and retirees' demographic variables of gender, and age, level of education, place of residence and income level with 7% experiences of anxiety. There were also significant relationships between stress and retirees' demographic factors of gender, age, and educational level, but no significant relationships found between place of residence and stress, with 6% experiences of stress found among retirees. According to World Health Organization (2017) statistics, over 20% of the adult population who have aged 60 and above suffer from one form of mental or neurological disorder (excluding headache disorders) and 6.6% of all disability (disability adjusted life years (DALYs) among people over 60 years is attributed to mental and neurological disorders. These disorders in older people account for 17.4% of Years Lived with Disability (YLDs). The most common mental and neurological disorders in among this age group According to WHO statistics are dementia and depression, which affect approximately 5% and 7% of the world's older population, respectively. Anxiety disorders affect 3.8% of the older population, substance use problems affect almost 1% and around a quarter of deaths from self-harm are among people aged 60 or above. Substance abuse problems among older people are often overlooked or misdiagnosed. It is crystal

Assessment of Causes of Mental Health ... (Aminu, et. al., 20203) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408112>

that the previous studies reviewed in this work left a gap behind to the best knowledge of the researchers, in the sense that none of them has investigated exactly the problem of the present study. Hence, the present study focused on assessment of the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

This study stands on the following objectives:

1. To asses causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State.
2. To determine whether there is any significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on gender.
3. To determine whether there is any significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on religion.
4. To determine whether there is any significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on year of retirement.

Research Question

The following research question was raised and answered in this study:

What are the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were raised and tested in this study:

1. There is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on gender.
2. There is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on religion.
3. There is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on year of retirement.

Methodology

The researchers adopted the descriptive survey research design. This type of design allows researchers to describe a phenomenon under study as they occur without an influence from the researchers. Descriptive survey method however, also the researchers to make observation of certain thing under study, collect relevant information about such phenomenon are describe them objectively. In this context, the researchers are not allowed to manipulate any variable. The population of this study comprised all retired civil servants in the state ministries and parastatals, retired teachers and retired local government staff in Ifelodun Local Government of Kwara State. This covers a total number of 854 retirees captured in the field survey carried on by the researchers from nine districts that formed Ifelodun local government area of Kwara State (these districts are; Idofian, Omupo, Ora, Share, Agunjin, Ile-Ire, Igbaja, Okeode and Oro-Ago). A multi-stage sampling technique which involved purposive, stratified, and simple random was used in selecting sample for this study. At stage one, only retirees that exist the public service or retired from active service from 2013 till-date (that is; 10 years ago), were purposively selected to avoid third party responses which might occur as a result of over age on the part of the respondents. At stage two, stratified sampling technique was used to select sample of this study based on some category of demographic characteristics such as gender, religion and year of retirement. Lastly, simple random sampling technique was used to select 120 participants from four (4) districts selected to participate in this study selected represents 14.05%. This figure is in line with Krejcie and Morgan sample size recommendation which suggests 10% as an adequate representation of a fair larger population like the population of this study.

A researchers self-designed and structured questionnaire which was titled "Causes of Mental Health Challenges Questionnaire (CMHCQ)" was used to elicit information on causes of mental health challenges as expressed by retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State. The instrument has two distinct sections: That is; section A and section B. Section A elicits personal data of the respondents such as gender, religion and year of retirement, while the section B consists of 20 items on the respondents' perception of the causes of mental health challenges. The 4-point Likert-type rating scale response format was used for respondents to make their precise responses to each item on the instrument which was tagged (CMHCQ). In order to ascertain the validity of the instrument of this study, some draft copies of the instrument were given to five seasoned lecturers in the Department of Counsellor Education, University of Ilorin for vetting. Minor corrections were observed on the instrument in the course of its vetting which were some few spelling and typographic errors that were later corrected before the final draft of the instrument. The instrument was re-presented to the same lecturers who vetted it earlier and it was affirmed

Assessment of Causes of Mental Health ... (Aminu, et. al., 20203) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408112>

been valid. In order to ascertain the reliability of the instrument, test re-test reliability method was used. By this means, the instrument was administered on twenty (20) retirees within the study locale who did not form part of this study again, but possessed similar characteristics of the population of the study. After a period of four (4) weeks, the same instrument was re-administered on the same set of retirees. The two set of scores obtained on the two occasions were later correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistical method. The reliability co-efficient (r) value of 0.86 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the instrument is reliable for the study. Frequency counts and percentages were used to analyze the demographic data of the respondents of this study such as gender, religion and year of retirement.

The research question set for the study was answered with items analysis using Mean scores benchmark of 2.50. The researchers used Four Point Likert-Type Rating Scale format in the following order: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points; Agree (A) =3 points, disagree (D) =2 points, and Strongly Disagree (SD) =1 point. The highest score that any participant can score is 4 and the lowest is 1. However, the average score is calculated thus: $1+2+3+4 = 10$, and $10/4 = 2.50$. However, any item that its mean score is above 2.50 would be considered as high causes of mental health challenges among the respondents, while those below it would be considered as low causes. Any item that its mean score falls on 2.50 which is average mean score would be considered as neutral response. The three (3) null hypotheses formulated for the study were tested with t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The data obtained were analysed using frequency counts and percentage, mean rank order for descriptive data while t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistics were used to test the three (3) null hypotheses formulated for the study.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents Based on Gender, Religion and Year of Retirement.

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentages (%)
1.	Gender		
	Male	84	70.0
	Female	36	30.0
	Total	120	100.0
2.	Religion		
	Christianity	68	56.7
	Islam	45	37.5
	ATR	07	5.8
	Total	120	100.0
3.	Year of Retirement		
	2013-2017	74	62.0
	2018-2023	46	38.0
	Total	120	100.0

Source: Field Survey

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents based on gender, religious affiliation and year of retirement. The total number of respondents who participated in this study was 120. Based on the gender of the respondents, 84 (70.0%) were male and 36 (30.0%) were female. On the basis of religious affiliation of the respondents 68 (56.7%) were Christianity, 45 (37.5%) were Muslims and 7 (5.8%) were from other African Traditional Religion background. Lastly, based on the year of retirement of the respondents, those who had retired between 2013 and 2017 were 74 (62.0%), while those who had retired between 2018 and 2023 were 46 (38.0%).

Research Question 1: What are the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Items Analysis of Causes of Mental Health Challenges among Retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State, Nigeria

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Experience of abuse/inhuman treatment/discrimination	2.94	0.88	High
2	Genetic factor/hereditary factor	3.04	0.86	High
3	Reduced level of physical activities	2.98	0.76	High
4	Poor nutrition/hygiene	3.10	0.98	High

Assessment of Causes of Mental Health ... (Aminu, et. al., 20203) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408112>

5	Absence of functional intervention programme	3.34	1.26	High
6	Poor access to functional healthcare	2.85	1.04	High
7	Childhood abuse at the early stage of life	2.58	0.74	High
8	Brain malfunction/defects/injury	3.28	1.32	High
9	Bereavement (e.g., loss of close relation)	2.82	1.08	High
10	Persistent domestic violence	3.02	0.77	High
11	Poverty/financial burden	2.80	0.93	High
12	Financial unpreparedness	3.20	1.36	High
13	Poor interpersonal/family relationship	3.08	1.20	High
14	Increasing future uncertainty (e.g., nonpayment of gratuity)	2.96	1.02	High
15	Absence of income generating activities	2.76	0.87	High
16	Increasing prevalence of diseases due to old age	2.66	1.13	High
17	Social alienation/isolation/neglect	3.06	1.24	High
18	Post-traumatic experience (e.g., witness of assassination)	2.64	0.79	High
19	Substance misuse/drug abuse	3.01	0.94	High
20	Reduced or lack of adequate sleep	2.68	0.85	High
Grand Total		2.94		

Source: *Field Survey, 2023*

The table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of items on the causes of mental health challenges as expressed by the retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State, Nigeria. There are twenty items altogether on the (CMHCQ) questionnaire that were statistically analysed. Item 5 with a statement "absence of functional intervention programme" has the highest mean score of 3.34, item 8 with a statement "brain malfunction/defects/injury" has a mean score of 3.28 and item 12 with a statement "financial unpreparedness" has a mean score of 3.20 respectively. From the table presented above, it is crystal clear that all items on the table were factors that responsible for mental health challenges among the retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State, Nigeria as none of the items was rated below 2.5 which was used as the benchmark for decision making.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State based on gender.

Table 3: Mean, SD and t-test Result Showing Difference in Causes of Mental Health Challenges among Retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State Based on Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	Cal. t	Crit. t	p-value	Decision
Male	84	54.04	6.82	118	0.82	1.96	0.126	Retained
Female	36	36.84	4.64					

Source: *Field Survey*

Table 3 shows that for a degree of freedom (df) of 118, the calculated t value of 0.82 is less than the critical t-value of 1.96, with a corresponding p-value of 0.124 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there was no significant difference in the opinion of retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara on the causes of mental health challenges based on gender. Hence, the hypothesis one which stated that there is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State based on gender is retained.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State based on religion.

Assessment of Causes of Mental Health ... (Aminu, et. al., 20203) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408112>

Table 4: ANOVA Result Showing Difference in the Respondents' View of Causes of Mental Health Challenges among Retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State Based on Religion.Source:

Source	Df	SS	Means Square	Cal. F-ratio	Crit. F-ratio	p-value
Between Group	2	106.168	54.084			
Within Group	117	5268.355	45.028	0.84	3.00	0.556
Total	119	5345.360				

Field Survey

Table 4 shows that the calculated F-ratio of 0.84 is less than the critical F-ratio of 3.00 ($p = 0.556 > 0.05$). This means that there was no significant difference in the opinion of retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara on the causes of mental health challenges based on religion. Thus, the hypothesis two which stated that there is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State based on religion is accepted.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on year of retirement.

Table 5: Mean, SD and t-test Result Showing Difference in Causes of Mental Health Challenges among Retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State Based on Year of Retirement

Year of Retirement	N	Mean	SD	Df	Cal. t	Crit. t	p-value	Decision
2013-2017	74	62.16	7.24					
2018-2023	46	48.94	6.84	118	2.08	1.96	0.001	Rejected

Source: *Field Survey*

Table 5 shows that for a degree of freedom (df) of 118, the calculated t-value of 2.08 is greater than the critical value of 1.96, with a corresponding p-value of 0.001 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there was significant difference in the opinion of retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara on the causes of mental health challenges based on year of retirement. Hence, the hypothesis three which stated that there is no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on year of retirement is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that absence of functional intervention programme, brain malfunction/defect/injury and financial unpreparedness are the major causes of mental health challenges among the retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State, Nigeria. The first finding stated above is in line with the findings of Temilola (2022) whose study discovered similar outcome in its findings. The second finding of this study is also in agreement with the findings of Aminu, Yahaya, Adigun, Aminullahi and Adio (2021) who study also comes up with the same result that one of the major reasons why people have psychological problem such as depression is as a result of brain injury. The third finding of the present study is also in tandem with the findings of Ugwu and Idemudia (2023) whose recently conducted study unveiled the same empirical outcome. The agreement in the present findings and the previous ones might not be surprising in the sense that all the studies were locally conducted and as such they are home based studies with closeness in some characteristics of the respondents.

Hypothesis one tested revealed that there was no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun LGA., Kwara State based on gender. The finding is in consistence with the finding of the study of Ejeh, Achor and Ejeh (2019) who had earlier discovered the same thing in their empirical analysis. Hypothesis two unveiled that no significant difference occurred in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State based on religion. The finding is in agreement with the finding of a study conducted by of Aminu, Yahaya, Adigun, Aminullahi and Adio (2021) which maintained that respondents were not differ in their responses on the causes of depressive disorder on the basis of religion.

The result of hypothesis three indicated that there was significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area, Kwara State based on year of retirement. This finding is in consistence with the findings of study of Daramola, Awunor and Akande (2019) and Ejeh, Achor and Ejeh (2019) whose different empirical

Assessment of Causes of Mental Health ... (Aminu, et. al., 20203) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408112>

findings indicated that age has significant implication in the experience of challenges that were bedeviling retired class and elderly population of Nigeria.

Conclusions

The findings identified absence of functional intervention programme, brain malfunction/defect/injury and financial unpreparedness as the leading causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State, Nigeria. The result of the hypotheses revealed that there was no significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State, Nigeria based on gender and religion but discovered a significant difference in the causes of mental health challenges among retirees in Ifelodun local government area., Kwara State, Nigeria based on year of retirement.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of the study, it is recommended among other things that:

1. There should be provision for different functional intervention programmes that will make life conducive for all retirees after retirement irrespective of where they had worked.
2. Mental healthcare should be strengthened in every nook and cranny of the country to allow easy access to preventive, and treatment intervention programmes at very low or no cost for all citizens.
3. The workers should be trained on how to plan for retirement and be assisted to achieve such plans.
4. Irrespective of gender and religious backgrounds of the retirees, they should be encouraged to seek assistance or help on their mental health challenges.
5. The people who had been long retired (for instance, above five years) should be given a close monitoring and adequate attentions by all concerned stakeholders for improved living standard.

References

- Aminu, H. P., Yahaya, L. A., Adigun, A. A., Aminullahi, S. A. & Adio, A. A. (2021). Perceived causes of depression as expressed by undergraduates of Universities in Kwara State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Social Science Research*, 4 (6), 104-133. ISSN 2581-5148.
- Daramola, O.E., Awunor, N.S. & Akande, T.M. (2019). The challenges of retirees and older persons in Nigeria: A need for close attention and urgent action. *International Journal of Tropical Disease & Health*, 1, 23-34. DOI: 10.9734/IJTDH/2018/v34i430099
- Ejeh, V., Achor, E. & Ejeh, E.E. (2019). An Examination of associated factors of emotional health problems among retirees in Kogi State, Nigeria. *South Asian Research Journal of Nursing and Healthcare*, 1 (1), 34-44. DOI:10.36346/SARJNHC.2019.v01i01.006
- Galderisi, S., Heinz, A., Kastrup, M., Beezhold, J. & Sartorius, N. (2017). A proposed new definition of mental health. *Psychiatry Pol.* 51 (3), 407-411. DIO: <https://doi.org/10.12740/pp/74145>
- Haruna, A. S., & Mayanchi, M. L. (2023). Mental Health Status of Lecturers in Federal University Gusau Amidst Banditry in Zamfara State: Implications for Counselling and Psychotherapy. *Academic Journal of Psychology and Counseling*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.22515/ajpc.v5i1.7630>
- Jon Ivar, E. & Steinar, K. (2003). Social causation, health selective mobility, and the reproduction of socioeconomic health inequalities over time: Panel study of adult men. *Social Science Medicine*, 57, 1475– 1489. doi: 10.1016/s0277-9536[02]00514-2.
- Patel, V., Belkin, G. S., Chockalingham, A., Cooper, J., Saxena, S. & Unutzer, J. (2013). Grand challenges: Integrating mental health services into priority care platforms. *PLOS Med*, 10, e1001448.10.1371/journal.pmed.1001448
- Temilola, O. M. (2022). Investigating post-retirement challenges among the older retirees in Ikotun-Alimosho Community, Lagos State. *Benin Journal of Social Work and Community Development*, 4, 1-11. <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-328X/13/5/425>
- Ugwu, L.E. & Idemudia, E.S. (2023). Retirement planning and financial anxiety among Nigerian civil servants: Insights from social comparison theory. *Behavioural Science*, 13 (5), 425.
- Wang, Q. (2022). Review on definitions of mental health and related concepts. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 670, 991-995.
- World Health Organization. (2017). *Mental health of older adults*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mental-health-of-older-adults>